

PERCEPTIONS OF EDUCATION ROLE IN DEVELOPING SOCIETY

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance and problems of study and education's place in our community.

Keywords: contemporary education, developing, society, social change

Introduction: The role of education as an agent or instrument of social change and development is now widely recognized.

Social change happens when people need change. Where existing social systems or networks of social institutions fail to meet existing human needs, and where new material suggests better ways to meet human needs. Although education is seen as an important vector in society, it is largely given a conservative role as its primary function is to socialize young people and maintain social order. In this era of rapid social change, the role of education in serving the nation is emphasized. If the economy is doing well, more educational experiments will be supported and more idealistic goals such as equal educational opportunities will be pursued. But in the realm of ideology and morality, education is most clearly given a leading role. Social change occurs in response to different kinds of changes that occur in social and non-social environments. Education can bring about social change by changing people's worldviews and attitudes. It can bring about changes in patterns of social relationships, thereby producing social change.

Method of analysis: This have a look at used the thematic overview method with ATLAS.ti 9. the thematic evaluate is a device brought by Zairul (2020, 2021), which changed into used due to the fact this studies technique applies the thematic evaluation

method within the literature evaluation process. Clarke and Braun (2013) described thematic evaluation because the identity of the version and production of subject matters throughout an in-intensity studying of the topic. In this observe, the subsequent steps have been taken to become aware of styles and construct issues for teachers' perceptions and tendencies within the ethical training curriculum. The look at's intention become to investigate and interpret the findings to signify destiny studies on teachers' perceptions of the ethical curriculum. The literature turned into decided on consistent with numerous criteria: at the least the keyword(s) teachers' perception, teachers' perspective, teachers' views, and morals.

The reassets for the literature have been the Web Science databases of Clarivate Analytics and Scopus of Elsevier. The Science Network changed into decided on for all journals listed with an effect element measured within the Journal Citation Report (Jamal et al., 2008). Scopus become decided on as it has the most important series of peer-reviewed literature. A clear out out changed into implemented within the Web of Science using "form of documents," article types, and court cases papers, however now no longer reviews. The ultimate facts units contained the evaluation criteria: "Title, Keywords, and Abstract." The following key phrases have been used as seek terms: teachers' perception, teachers' perspective, teachers' views, ethical training, and ethical schooling curriculum

Results and analysis: Education has become one of the influential tools of social change in India. It has led to the mobilization of people's desire for development and change. Therefore, in today's complex national societies, education can neither be seen as a dominant force to protect cultural heritage nor as an agent of social change. It can only be seen as a collaborative force to bring about social change determined by the forces having greater power in society., needs to be completely reviewed. Laws must take into account regional differences in each state. The public must recognize new developments

Today's education is designed to promote the values of an urban competitive consumer society. Through its well-developed education system, India has produced a large number of scholars, professionals and technocrats over the past 50 years, excelling in their respective fields and making a name for themselves at the national and international level. The best scientists, doctors, engineers, researchers, professors, etc. are those who received their entire education in India, not those educated abroad. It's not about how education gets people employed, it's about making modern technology accessible to the poor and disadvantaged. It's a matter of quality of education. Instead of viewing population growth as a mere liability, let's control it and

turn it into an asset and an advantage. This can only be achieved through education and human development.

The three main shortcomings of the current education system are: (1) Current education does not produce or integrate the kinds of knowledge that are relevant to a changing society. (2) Technology associated with a particular body of knowledge is not suitable for our level of development in terms of employability or investment requirements.

Education fails to provide the framework of values upon which our country can prepare its committed politicians, bureaucrats, technocrats, and trusted professionals, and an elaborate system of support services has failed to bring the country to its peak. help. Level carry-on level. However, education does not guarantee high status and high status for everyone But without education, a person is unlikely to achieve social mobility. Gore argues that education plays a role in equality of opportunity in three ways, by making education accessible to all who desire it; Ability to benefit from this facility;

By developing educational content that encourages development A scientific and objective point of view. (3) by creating a social environment of mutual tolerance based on religion; language, caste, class, etc. It is very important to provide equal opportunities for social mobility and equal opportunities for good education for all in society.

How education relates to equal opportunity Based on the results of an empirical study conducted in eight states in 1967 on the social origins (age, sex, caste, father's occupation, father's education, etc.) of students at various levels of high school, college, and vocational school.

Based on In this study, two population group proposals were presented. (1) Education is a priority for white-collar groups, children in this group use educational institutions more than other groups, and children in this group use educational institutions more than other groups. (2) People who do not belong to white-collar groups can also receive education (see Gore, 1994:33). If the first argument is correct, it would underscore the futility of educating non-worker groups in our society. Education, social change, modernization :- Education was accepted as an important socializing agent, and teachers and educational institutions were accepted as socializing agents. In order to explain education as a means of social change, three things are important: the agent of change, the content of change, and the people to be changed, i.e., the social background of the students.

Educational institutions under the control of various cultural groups reflect the values of the groups that support and manage education. In these situations, teachers teach children certain values, aspirations and goals.

Educated social reformers emphasize values such as the elimination of caste limits, equality of women, the elimination of socially harmful social customs and practices, the right to have a say in the governance of the country, and the establishment of democratic institutions. Therefore, they wanted to teach liberal philosophy through education in order to transform society. In other words, they saw education as the flame or light of knowledge that dispels the darkness of ignorance.

During the 1960s and 1970s, there was an emphasis on using education to propagate modernization values. A productive economy, distributive justice, people's participation in decision-making bodies, and the introduction of science and technology into industry, agriculture and other occupations were embraced as the goals of modernization of Indian society.

And these goals should be achieved through liberal education.

Broader social environment changes :-Changes occur throughout the social environment surrounding society. It could be due to some internal or external force occurring in other societies. Social phenomena occurring in societies nearby or far away today have a very far-reaching impact. For example, English is now the world language for the dissemination of knowledge. As a result, India believes it needs to emphasize the need to maintain and enhance its knowledge of the English language in order to continue to benefit from the new knowledge spreading around the world. The world has evolved. Changes in social goals, objectives and values:-Social change can lie in society's goals, goals, and values. Changes can be in social values that directly affect the content of social roles and social interactions. For example, the acceptance of equality as a value ultimately translates into compulsory and free primary education, the extension of primary education to all children up to the age of 14, and the provision of financial and other assistance to junior classes. may be connected. Join an extended educational institution. Institutional social change

Societal change can be 'institutional', including changes in specific structures such as organizational forms, roles, and role content. The introduction of democracy and adult suffrage in India has made electoral education on responsible and responsive citizenship essential. This can ultimately affect the content and methods of teaching in educational institutions and teacher-teacher relationships. Changes in knowledge and technology Changes may be in existing knowledge and technology.

Space exploration, industrialization, agricultural and domestic engineering, the development of mass media for transportation and communication, new

understandings of the human organism, individual and social behavior, have greatly expanded knowledge and contributed to ever-expanding scientific and technological part of the field. Developments in knowledge and technology can therefore lead to changes in curricula, teaching and assessment methods, and the role of teachers. Changes in population size and composition The change can be in the size and composition of the population. A population explosion with different growth rates in different regions, communities, socioeconomic groups and age groups can require many changes in the education system. Students with different levels of intelligence and educational aspirations belonging to different socio-economic classes, different castes and religious groups are now enrolled in the same type of educational institutions and packed into the same classrooms. All these changes require changes in the education system as well.

As such, the various social changes that occur in society make the existing education system dysfunctional to some extent, adding pressure to change over time. Social Changes and Delays in the Indian Education System In response to social changes, the educational system must also change.

Changes are in line with social changes and can adequately meet the new goals and demands of different social groups.

Otherwise, there will be a lag between the goals and demands of society and those of the educational system. There are many such delays in the post-independence Indian education system, which in many ways play a dysfunctional role in Indian society. This was very clearly accepted by the Kothari Commission. It reported: "The existing education system is known to be largely dead, with wide gaps between its content and objectives and national development concerns. Instead of actively promoting awareness-raising, some features of the education system tend to be divisive: caste loyalty is encouraged in many private educational institutions; the former attend better private schools that charge tuition, and the latter are forced to do so.

Conclusion: Education has become one of the influential tools of social change in India. It has led to the mobilization of people's desire for development and change. Therefore, in today's complex national societies, education can neither be seen as a dominant force to protect cultural heritage nor as an agent of social change. It can only be seen as a collaborative force to bring about social change determined by the forces having greater power in society., needs to be completely reviewed. Laws must take into account regional differences in each state. The public must recognize new developments.

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